

ARE OT LAWS NECESSARY TODAY?

By

W. Stanley Jones

INTRODUCTION

In the third century AD, Rabbi Simlai undertook the task of enumerating every law found in the *Torah*. He concluded that the *Torah* contained **613 commandments**—248 positive (do's) corresponding to the parts of the human body, and 365 prohibitions (do not's) matching the days of the year.¹ When Jesus was asked which commandment was the greatest (Mark 12:28), He distilled the entire 613 into just two: to **love God wholly** (Deut 6:5) and to **love one's neighbor** as oneself (Lev 19:18). However, many of these 613 laws—such as avoiding mixed fabrics (Lev 19:19; Deut 22:11) or observing sabbatical and Jubilee years (Lev 25)—are no longer practiced today. This raises key questions:

- Are we still required to follow all 613 laws?
- If not, how do we discern which ones apply today?
- What value do these OT laws hold for the modern Church?

To address these questions, this study will trace the **historical response** to the law's interpretation and application—from its origins in Israel through the ministry of Jesus, the early Church, and the Reformation. This paper will examine the intent and enduring principles of the OT laws to understand their relevance in the life of the contemporary Church.

HISTORICAL ORIGIN

The notion that these 613 laws appeared like manna from heaven invites reconsideration. The people of that era were aware of the legal traditions that circulated around them. Indeed, what Moses communicated to Israel stands out as profoundly elevated when compared with the surrounding law codes known through archaeology, such as the *Code of Hammurabi*

¹ Israel Abrahams, *Judaism* (London: Archibald Constable & Co. Ltd., 1907), 28, <https://archive.org/details/judaism01abragoog/page/n40>.

(discovered in 1901).² Scholars have shown that other Ancient West Asian collections—the Akkadian, Hittite, and Middle Assyrian Code—addressed similar social concerns.³ The background in Leviticus 18:1–5 illuminates that Israel was not to imitate the customs of Egypt or Canaan, which provides evidence of the practices prevalent at the time. Moses declaring later, “**What great nation has laws as righteous as these?**” (Deut 4:8) is another proof of Israel’s law being better than other laws around. The question then arises whether Yahweh Himself should be understood as a lawgiver. As John H. Walton explains, the *Torah* is best understood not as ‘law’ but as ‘instruction’ or ‘revelation.’ The laws were not presented as isolated codes but as covenant stipulations within a divine treaty between Yahweh and Israel.⁴ Thus, the *Torah* represents both divine revelation and human mediation: it reveals God’s will for His people rather than imposing civil legislation.

CHRIST’S REINTERPRETATION

In the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus’ teaching astonished His listeners by the authority with which He engaged the law. Declaring that “He came not to abolish the law or the Prophets, but to fulfil them” (Matt 5:17), Jesus reoriented how the law was to be understood and practised. His reinterpretation can be observed in three ways. **First**, some commandments were elevated beyond their literal application. Anger was equated with murder (Matt 5:21–22), lustful intent with adultery (5:27–28), and retaliation replaced with non-resistance (Matt 5:38–39). Even love was expanded to include one’s enemies (Matt 5:43–44). **Second**, certain laws were nullified. Jesus’ statement that nothing outside a person can defile them (Mark 7:15) effectively dissolved dietary restrictions. Even divorce was redefined by returning to God’s original intent (Matt 19:1–9). Jesus also condemned traditions that nullified God’s command (Mark 7:9). **Third**, Jesus at times placed demands that exceeded the law’s boundaries. To the rich man, He said, ‘Sell all you have’ (Mark 10:17–22)—a command that could be viewed as a figurative 614th law, given to one who professed to have kept all the others. This shows that Jesus looked beyond external obedience. In his book *Jesus and Judaism*, E. P. Sanders engages with the diversity of scholarly interpretations regarding Jesus and the law. He argues that while Jesus may have challenged certain aspects

² Victor H. Matthews and Don C. Benjamin, *Old Testament Parallels: Laws and Stories from the Ancient Near East*, 3rd ed. (New York: Paulist Press, 2006), 105.

³ Matthews and Benjamin, *Old Testament Parallels*, 103,115,120.

⁴ John H. Walton, *Ancient Near Eastern Thought and the Old Testament: Introducing the Conceptual World of the Hebrew Bible*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2018), Chapter 13.

of the law, He did not intend to oppose it in principle; rather, His actions reflect careful engagement and reinterpretation, not outright rejection.⁵

APOSTOLIC DECISION

The Jerusalem Council (Acts 15) had to face the challenge posed by the Mosaic Law, particularly the command in **Exodus 12:48**, which stipulated that circumcision was necessary for Gentiles to be part of the covenant community. The council did not reject the law but waived circumcision. However, the council also upheld certain aspects of the law, “instructing believers to abstain from food offered to idols, from sexual immorality, from the meat of strangled animals, and from consuming blood” (Acts 15:20). The apostles concluded that the full weight of the law—“a yoke that neither we nor our ancestors have been able to bear” (Acts 15:10)—should not be imposed. The *South Asia Bible Commentary* observes that this recalls the prohibitions of **Leviticus 18**, including incest, intermarriage outside the covenant, bestiality, and homosexuality.⁶ This suggests that the early Church did not regard the law as abolished but rather reoriented it toward ethical and moral formation under the new covenant.

REFORMATION CONTROVERSY

After the Reformation, Protestant preaching often emphasised the gospel, which failed to address the law. John Agricola, a close associate of Luther, became so focused on grace alone that he dismissed the law entirely. Luther had to correct his own opinion and then strongly condemned this view, labelling such proponents antinomians, meaning ‘against the law.’

Luther wrote during the **Antinomian disputation (1537-1540)**:

How can one know what sin is without the law and conscience? And how will we learn what Christ is, what he did for us, if we do not know what the law is that he fulfilled for us? ...

For who could know what and why Christ suffered for us without knowing what sin or law is?⁷

This debate brings into attention the danger of neglecting the law and the necessity of observing it within its covenantal and moral context.

⁵ Sanders, E. P. *Jesus and Judaism*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1985, 246.

⁶ Babu Immanuel Venkataraman, “Acts,” in *South Asia Bible Commentary: A One-Volume Commentary on the Whole Bible*, ed. Brian Wintle (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan Academic, 2015), commentary on Acts 15:20.

⁷ Martin Luther, “Against the Antinomians,” trans. Martin H. Bertram, in *Luther’s Works*, vol. 47, *The Christian in Society IV*, ed. Franklin Sherman (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1971), 113.

MODERN APPLICATION

The law remains a vital reference. In most cases, the text must be studied carefully in relation to other passages, always with a view to our relationship with both God and others. The new covenant foundation says that “I will write the laws in their hearts” (Jer 31:33). Considering that, the laws are to be focused on the function rather than the form. For example, Paul uses **Deuteronomy 25:4** ‘not to muzzle a threshing ox’ to benefit those who ‘work in the ministry to be supported financially’ in **1 Corinthians 9:9**.

Confusion may arise when the holiness code is interpreted merely as a call to external holiness (1 Pet 1:16). True holiness is a conscious choice to imitate God, and grasping the purpose of the laws, rather than merely observing their outward form, is central to understanding what it means to be ‘set apart.’⁸ For example, if one wants to abstain from drinking wine, despite the Bible’s encouragement (**1 Tim 5:23**), let them do so; for God will honour their faith and obedience like the Rechabites, who never drank wine (**Jer 35**).⁹ On the other hand, if one wishes to continue drinking as part of the cultural activity. They should not be judged, nor should anyone impose a law by selectively applying certain Bible verses.

The OT laws were never intended as a comprehensive legal code; rather, Jesus’ teachings and Paul’s writings show that one must interpret them considering their purpose and context. God values voluntary faithfulness, not legalistic conformity. OT laws reveal the very character of God who gave the law.¹⁰ This understanding is exemplified long before Sinai in the life of Joseph. He discerned what was right when he refused the advances of Potiphar’s wife, recognizing that such an act would be ‘**a sin against God**’ (**Gen 39:9**). His moral consciousness did not arise from an external command but from an internal alignment with

⁸ The command to be holy is drawn from Leviticus 11:44; 19:2; and 20:7, 26, and is echoed in Romans 12:1; 1 Corinthians 6:19–20; and Ephesians 2:21–22, calling believers to present themselves as living sacrifices to God. “In the OT, holiness (*qōdeš*) denotes a positive cultic or moral condition associated with God, people, things, places, or time—either inherent or achieved through ritual means. It is defined both by consistency with God’s character and by separation from impurity”. “In the NT, *hagios* describes the attribute of God that His people are called to reflect (Luke 1:75; 2 Cor 7:1; Eph 4:24).” See Geoffrey Wainwright, “Holiness,” in *The Oxford Companion to the Bible*, ed. Bruce M. Metzger and Michael D. Coogan (New York: Oxford University Press, 1993), 285–86; and David Noel Freedman, ed., *The Anchor Bible Dictionary* (New York: Doubleday, 1992), 3629,3645, <https://archive.org/details/anchor-bible-dictionary-6-volumes/page/n3629/mode/2up>.

⁹ In Jeremiah 35, the Rechabites abstained from wine out of obedience to their ancestor Jonadab’s command, even though such abstinence was not required by the Mosaic Law. Their faithfulness is commended by God as an example of obedience and integrity, not as a new law.

¹⁰ Christopher J. H. Wright, *Living as the People of God: The Relevance of Old Testament Ethics* (Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1983), 34.

the divine character. Likewise, his diligence in serving Potiphar reflected wholehearted devotion to the Lord, echoing the principle later expressed in **Colossians 3:23**: ‘**as working for the Lord.**’ Such examples show that true obedience does not depend on written regulations but on a heart transformed by God’s Spirit. In this way, the modern believer fulfils the intent of the law—living by love, integrity, and reverence for God—rather than by rigid adherence to its letter.

CONCLUSION

To illustrate that law remains a valuable resource for discernment and correction, consider the following analogy. Jude, a young boy from a village, knew all the roads by heart because his father had taught him well. His father had also given him a map and advised him to keep it close, even though Jude rarely needed to use it. One evening, returning home tired and disoriented, he lost his way. Remembering his father’s advice, he consulted the map, recognized his mistake, and found his way home. Likewise, the law functions as a reference point for the believer—a guide to reveal where one has strayed and to realign one’s heart with God’s direction.

OT laws are not obsolete but fulfilled and transformed in Christ. They still teach us God’s holiness, justice, and mercy. As Paul declares, “Christ is the end of the law” (Rom 10:4) and the law served as a tutor leading to Christ (Gal 3:24–25), and now, under the new covenant, the law is written on our hearts. Instead of asking which laws still bind, the Church must seek the spirit and purpose of the law, embodying its fulfilment in Christ through lives marked by love, justice, and holiness.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abrahams, Israel. *Judaism*. London: Archibald Constable & Co. Ltd., 1907.
<https://archive.org/details/judaism01abrargoog/page/n6/mode/2up>.
- Freedman, David Noel, ed. *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*. 6 vols. New York: Doubleday, 1992. <https://archive.org/details/anchor-bible-dictionary-6-volumes/mode/2up>.
- Luther, Martin. “Against the Antinomians.” Translated by Martin H. Bertram. In *Luther’s Works*, Vol. 47, *The Christian in Society IV*, edited by Franklin Sherman, 107–119. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1971.
- Matthews, Victor H., and Don C. Benjamin. *Old Testament Parallels: Laws and Stories from the Ancient Near East*. 3rd ed. New York: Paulist Press, 2006.
- Sanders, E. P. *Jesus and Judaism*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1985.
- Venkataraman, Babu Immanuel. “Acts.” In *South Asia Bible Commentary: A One-Volume Commentary on the Whole Bible*, edited by Brian Wintle, Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan Academic, 2015.
- Wainwright, Geoffrey. “Holiness.” In *The Oxford Companion to the Bible*, edited by Bruce M. Metzger and Michael D. Coogan, 285–286. New York: Oxford University Press, 1993.
- Walton, John H. *Ancient Near Eastern Thought and the Old Testament: Introducing the Conceptual World of the Hebrew Bible*. 2nd ed. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2018.
- Wright, Christopher J. H. *Living as the People of God: The Relevance of Old Testament Ethics*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 1983.